

Speculation on the Energy-Time Uncertainty Relation for Bound States

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In a recent paper (1), it is argued that “ Δt ” in Heisenberg’s energy-time uncertainty relation $(\Delta E)(\Delta t) \geq \hbar/2$ ((1)) is often taken to be elapsed time and not the variance of time. In (1) a time independent derivation based on $E_{\text{system}} + E_{\text{environment}} = E_{\text{constant}}$ is developed, suggesting energy fluctuations in E_{system} i.e. the quantum system. In a recent note (2), we argued that for the momentum-position uncertainty principle: $\Delta p \Delta x \geq \hbar/2$ ((2)), $\langle pp \rangle$ and $\langle xx \rangle$ are proportional to average kinetic and potential energy for an oscillator, with the ground state being the lowest energy level and yielding an equality. We showed that using average energy values $\langle pp/2m \rangle = \langle k/2 xx \rangle$ one immediately obtains ((2)) for the ground state with an equal sign. No use of the environment is made. In this note, we argue that ((1)) should follow from similar considerations i.e. one may consider ΔE and Δt for the ground state oscillator or other bound wavefunctions. This begs the question: What should be used for ΔE and Δt ? $\langle W | H | W \rangle - E^*E = 0$ if W is an eigenstate. We argue that $a(p,t) = \exp(-iEt) a(p)$ where energy at a point x is $P(p/x) \text{energy}(p,x) = W(x)[pp/2m + V(x)] a(p,t) \exp(ipx)$. It seems for the time independent case energy itself fluctuates within the period $1/E$. We keep the real part of $\exp(-iEt)$ i.e. $|\cos(\omega t)|$. In previous notes, we have argued that negative $\cos(\omega t)$ or $\cos(px)$ terms represent motion opposite to general flow given by $F = -dV/dx$, so we use $|\cos(\omega t)|$. Thus, energy fluctuates as $E |\cos(\omega t)|$ within a period $1/E$. For time probability, we use dt/T . This leads to an expression for all wavefunctions (not just the oscillator ground state) of:

$\Delta E \Delta t = .56 \hbar$ which is a little higher than $.5 \hbar$.

Historical Issues

There seem to exist historical issues related to the energy-time uncertainty principle (see (1)). Δt is often taken to be the classical time needed to transverse a certain length and ΔE an error in E (of the order of E). The time-energy uncertainty principle does not follow from the general commutator approach which may be used to derive the momentum-position uncertainty principle among others.

Conditional Probability

In quantum mechanics, much focus is given to $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction. We argue that one may focus on the conditional probability $P(p/x)$ because: $[\sum_p p^*p/2m P(p/x)] / W(x) + V(x) = E$ for each x . Important average physics already exists at each point. At each x there exists a momentum distribution which changes with x . So to calculate $\langle pp \rangle$, one may find $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ and multiply by $P(x) = WW$ (bound state) then integrate over x yielding: $\sum_p a(p)a(-p) p^*p$.

With respect to the variance squared of energy, one might at first consider:

$\langle W_0 H W_0 \rangle - \langle W_0 H W_0 \rangle \langle W_0 H W_0 \rangle = 0$ leading to no variance. Seen another way for the oscillator ground state:

$$(A) \quad \text{Sum over } x, p \quad P(x) P(p/x) (p^2/2m + .5kx^2) = E$$

$$(B) \quad \text{Sum over } x, p \quad P(x) P(p/x) (p^2/2m + .5kx^2)(p^2/2m + .5kx^2) \\ = 1/D \int dx \quad (kx^2 E - .25kx^4) \exp(-2ax^2) + \exp(-ax^2) (-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} [\\ (E - .5kx^2) \exp(-ax^2)] \quad \text{where } (1/D \text{ is the normalization constant of } \exp(-2ax^2)) \\ = 2EE + EE - 1/D \int dx \quad 4kx^2 \exp(-2ax^2) \\ = 2EE - 2EE + EE$$

This again leads to a 0 variance in E.

If one, however, writes the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $W(x)$ and $V(x)$ expressed as Fourier series and collects terms associated with $\exp(ipx)$, then:

$$p^2/2m a(p) + \text{Sum over } k \quad V(k)a(p-k) = E a(p) \quad ((3))$$

This suggests the RHS may be $\text{id}/\text{dt} \exp(iEt)$ and that $a(p)$ fluctuates in time in a resonance type manner. There is no x dependence in ((3))

Thus, at time t , one sees $E \cos(\omega t)$ and not the full energy, we argue. The full energy appears only if one takes an average ignoring time which is done when one uses $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The different p (momentum) values appear at different times. For time probability, we use dt/T . Then:

$$\langle E \rangle = 2E \int \sin(\omega t) dt/T \quad \text{from 0 to half a cycle} \quad (\text{Note: } \cos(\omega t) \text{ is replaced with } \sin \text{ for ease of calculation.})$$

$$\langle E \rangle = 4E/(T\omega) \quad ((3b)) \quad \text{Note that } \langle E \rangle \text{ is not equal to } E \text{ over the cycle time of } 1/E.$$

$$\langle EE \rangle = 2EE \int \sin(\omega t) \sin(\omega t) dt/T = 2EE/(T\omega) \cdot 3.14/2 = EE/2$$

$$\langle EE \rangle - \langle E \rangle \langle E \rangle = EE/2 - EE \cdot 4/(3.14 \cdot 3.14) \text{ approx} = EE \cdot .094 \quad ((4))$$

Next, one must calculate: $\text{var}(t) \cdot \text{var}(E) = \langle t^2 \rangle - \langle t \rangle^2$

$$\langle t \rangle = \int_0^T dt/T \cdot t = T/2 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle t^2 \rangle = T^2/3$$

$$\text{So } \text{var}(t) \cdot \text{var}(E) = T^2 \left(\frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} \right) = T^2/12 \quad ((5))$$

Then, with $E = \hbar \omega$ and $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 3.14/T$

$$\text{var}(t) \cdot \text{var}(E) = .56 \hbar \quad ((6))$$

((6)) holds for all bound state wavefunctions and in this calculation is related to cycling in the system.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the energy-time uncertainty principle should be applicable to bound states because time enters through $\exp(-iEt)$. Furthermore, we argue that Δt should be the variance of t and ΔE , the variance of E . At first, $\langle W^2 \rangle - \langle W \rangle^2 = 0$ seems to indicate no variance in E , but we argue that at each x (i.e. using conditional probabilities) $a(p,t) = \exp(-iEt)a(p)$. Thus, we consider $E = \hbar \omega |\cos(\omega t)|$ as the energy which appears at each t within a cycle of length $1/E$. This is independent of x . For time probability, we use dt/T . This allows for the calculation of ΔE and Δt and the product for all bound states is $.56 \hbar$. This is a little higher than $.5 \hbar$ and there is no inequality.

References

1. J.S. Briggs 2008 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 99 012002
<https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/99/1/012002/pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Momentum-Position Uncertainty Principle (preprint, zenodo, 2020)